

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF SINTERED MATRIX MATERIALS USED FOR FABRICATION OF DIAMOND AND CBN IMPREGNATED TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The work presents the interactions between processing of 90% Cu and 10% Sn powder mix, the type and amount of dopants introduced, the parameters of the compaction process, the structure of the resulting material and its mechanical and technical properties are considered. The application of the materials in the metal matrix of sintered superhard (diamond or cubic boron nitride) grinding tools for cutting and grinding glass and technical ceramics were investigated. The powders were unmilled and milled for 8 and 30 hours. The dopants were titanium and glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO–ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system. Cold compaction was in a rigid die and sintering carried out at 750 °C. All as-consolidated materials were subjected to density measurements, tested for hardness and excellent resistance to abrasion. The fracture surfaces and microstructures were examined by light microscopy (LM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The result showed that the addition of the ceramic phase in the form of glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system in amount of 5% by mass increases the hardness of sintered materials but decreases their wear resistance. In turn, the addition of titanium powders to metal matrix composite were provided materials characterized by high hardness and wear resistance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Superhard abrasive materials are required for tools to grinding process of new construction materials for aerospace, aviation, energy, automotive, machinery, utility and medical applications. From the early nineties metal bonded abrasive tools made of cubic boron nitride or diamond, which would work on conventional grinding machines in (near) standard processing conditions, have been developed. Modifying the matrix material in superhard tools can increase their performance characteristics, as well as grinding efficiency. Durability and efficiency of superhard tools, input power (electricity consumption) and productivity losses are mainly related to the design, structure and composition of the matrix material. Detailed knowledge regarding the operation of the tool, and the properties of the workpiece material (hardness, density, abrasive properties), allow proper selection of additives to be introduced into the matrix material in order to improve its mechanical and physical properties. Interaction between the matrix material and diamond or CBN grains also improves the adhesion of binder to the surface of diamond or CBN grains and hence tool life. Currently, the production of diamond tools for the processing of glass and technical ceramics is based on raw materials, including cobalt powders, alloy powders having the trade names of DIATABASE V21, Cobalite, Next and Keen; as well as blends of cobalt-based powders. Despite the high and growing price of cobalt and its harmful effects on health, it is still used in manufacturing professional tools, although the recent trend is towards a broader application of inexpensive, premixed and ball milled powders [1–4].

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Basing on earlier studies, Cu–Sn powders with glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system and Cu–Sn–Ti alloys, manufactured from inexpensive ball-milled powders by cold

compression in a rigid die and sintering at 750 °C, were chosen as potential cobalt substitutes in the manufacture of diamond impregnated segments for abrasive applications.

The starting materials were (Figure 1) electrolytic copper powder (LT16), water atomised prealloyed tin (45UM), fried ground glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system (Pb21K) and sponge titanium powders, provided by Stanchem, The Institute of Advanced Manufacturing Technology and Fluke, respectively.

Prior to milling the powders were mixed for 30 minutes in a Turbula T2C mixer. The mixture containing 85% copper, 10% tin and 5% glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system, was ball-milled in air at 70% critical speed for 8 and 30 hours, respectively. About 50% of the milling container was filled with 20 mm agate SiO₂ balls and ~10:1 ball-to-powder weight ratio was used. After ball milling the powders were tested for particle size and shape, and examined metallographically. The alloy made from pre-mixed powder and powder ball-milled for 8 hours of Cu–Sn–glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system were also subjected to X-ray phase analysis using a PANalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer using copper anode lamp ($\text{Cu}\lambda\ K\alpha = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$)

Figure 1: Starting powders: (a) LT 16 copper, (b) 45 UM tin, (c) Pb21K glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system, (d) titanium

Figure 2: Particle shapes (left) and microstructures (right) of as-mixed powders and of powders ball-milled for 8 and 30 hours

Sieve Analysis	Time of Milling	
	8 hours	30 hours
<38 µm	73,65%	89,75%
38 – 45 µm	10,89%	7,69%
45 – 63 µm	7,65%	1,26%
63 – 90 µm	5,65%	
>90	2,08%	

Table 1: Particle size distributions and tap densities of ball-milled powders

The ball-milled powders and the Cu-Sn-Ti powders were the poured into rectangular cavities of a high speed steel die and consolidated to near-full density by sintering for 1 hour at 750 °C and 160 MPa. The as-consolidated specimens were first tested for density and hardness using the water displacement method and Rockwell test, respectively, and then examined metallographically by light microscopy (LM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM on Jeol JSM 6460LV) and X-ray diffraction.

The specimens were tested also for resistance to 2-body abrasion by quartz sand on a Micro Wear Tester (MWT) [5–7]. A commercial Cu-Sn (90/10) alloy was also tested as a reference material. The wear measurements were of abrasive index (A_i), representing the average loss of height of the test piece per 20 m sliding distance. The test consisted of grinding the three test pieces ($1 \pm 0,01 \text{ cm}^2$ each) of each specimen (material) on #220 grit SiC abrasive paper for 30 s at a pressure of 800kPa with water as a coolant. The specimen holder and the backing – wheel were set into clock-wise motion at the same rotational speed of 150 rpm. This resulted in linear sliding velocity of 1,08 m/s. After each 30-s wear interval the test pieces were cleaned ultrasonically, dried and weighed to the nearest 0,1 mg. The abrasive index $A_i(2)$ for 2-body abrasion was calculated using eqn. (1).

$$A_i(p, v) = \frac{\Sigma \Delta M}{v \cdot A \cdot (2,38 + \rho_s)} 10^4 \left[\frac{\mu\text{m}}{20\text{m}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where

ΔM – mass loss of the test piece per 30-s wear interval [g]

v – sliding velocity [m/s]

A – wear surface of test specimen [cm^2] and

ρ_s – specific density of tested specimen [g/cm^3]

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of metallographic studies were shown in Figures 2 and 3, fractography in Figures 4 and 5. Table 1 presented the particle size distribution and the results of wear test are summarized in Table 2. X-ray diffraction patterns recorded for the tested materials are shown in Fig. 6 and 7. The phase identified in the test samples were summarized in Table 3.

Powder Time of Milling	Density (g/cm^3)	Rockwell Hardness Number	$A_i(2)$ ($\mu\text{m}/20\text{m}$)
Cu-Sn (90/10)	8,51	54	45,3
Pre-mixed	8,00	60	50,4
8 hours	7,68	69	83,9
30 hours	7,43	84	59,8
Cu-Sn-Ti	8,31	72	38,6

Table 2: As-consolidated densities, hardness numbers and mean abrasive wear indices

Figure 3: LM micrographs of the experimental alloys

Figure 4: Fracture surfaces of the as-mixed Cu-Sn-glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO-B₂O₃-SiO₂-PbO system alloy and EDS analysis of selected areas (wt.%): 1 i 2: 56Cu-5Sn-39Pb, 3 i 4: 92Cu-8Sn, 5, 6, 7: SiO₂, Zn(SiO₃)

Figure 5: Fracture surfaces of the alloy made from powder ball-milled for 8 hours of Cu–Sn–glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system alloy and EDS analysis of selected areas (wt.%): 1 i 2, 3: 39Pb–40Cu–6Sn, 4: Fe, 5: ZnO, Al₂O₃, 6: SiO₂, 7: Fe₂O₃, SiO₂, 8: Fe₂O₃, 9,10: 90Cu–10Sn

The powder mixture	The composition of the mixture, % mas	Identified phases and their space groups					
		Cu _{0.93} Sn _{0.07} F m-3m	Cu _{0.97} Sn _{0.03} F m-3m	Zn(SiO ₃)	SnO ₂	SiO ₂	B ₂ O
Cu–Sn (90/10)	90Cu–10Sn	a ₁ = 3.67977 Å	a ₂ = 3.639 Å				
Pre-mixed	85Cu–10Sn–5glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO–B ₂ O ₃ –SiO ₂ –PbO system	a ₁ = 3.67977 Å	a ₂ = 3.641214 Å	X	X	X	X
8 hours			a ₂ = 3.641214 Å	X	X	X	X
30 hours				a ₂ = 3.645820 Å	X	X	

Table 3: Characteristics of the phases identified in the tested samples with the specification of the amount of lattice parameter

Figure 6: X-ray diffraction patterns recorded for as-mixed Cu–Sn–glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system alloy

Figure 7: X-ray diffraction patterns recorded for alloy made from powder ball-milled for 8 hours of Cu–Sn–glass–crystalline materials from the ZnO–B₂O₃–SiO₂–PbO system

During milling the powder particles are repeatedly flattened, work-hardened and fractured, and welded together. After 30 hours of milling they showed flaky shape (Figure 2). The flaky shape decreased the average particle size of the powder, as measured by sieving. The mixture of powders

after 8 hours of milling contained above 15% grains above 63µm of grain size as evidenced by microscopy images.

After densification the alloys displayed high hardness, which increased with the milling time. From Figure 3 it is evident that all experimental alloys displayed fine-grained microstructure. The microscopic examination of the metallographic sections had revealed, however, marked differences in microstructural inhomogeneity of the tested specimens. Those manufactured from premixed powders showed a highly inhomogeneous distribution of structural components. For prolonged time of milling strong grain refinement had been observed. The as-sintered microstructure of material made of the powder milled for 30 hours was generally sub-micron-sized (Figure 3).

Both the ground and unground material revealed the presence of phases: solid solution-type Cu (Sn) having different lattice constants indicating the different solubility of Sn in a matrix of Cu and Zn(SiO₃), SnO₂, SiO₂, with H₂O.

With respect to the unground material was the simultaneous presence of two solid solutions of the type of Cu (Sn) having a space group F m-3m and a variety of lattice constants indicating the different solubilities of Sn (atomic radius R_{SN} = 1.40 Å) in a matrix of Cu (atomic radius r_{Cu} = 1.275 Å), respectively lattice constants a₁=3.67977Å and a₂=3.641214Å.

In the material after 8 and 30 hours of grinding was visible only one type of solid solution Cu (Sn) of space group F m-3m and lattice constant a₂ = 3.645820 Å. In the materials after 30 hours of grinding there was observed the phase of SiO₂.

CONCLUSIONS

The study provided detailed information of the effect of consolidation parameters, elemental powders of copper, tin, titanium, glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO-B₂O₃-SiO₂-PbO system on microstructure, hardness, density, and tribological properties of the materials.

The EDS examinations of the metallographic sections revealed marked differences in microstructural inhomogeneity between the alloy made from pre-mixed powder and powder ball-milled for 8 hours of Cu-Sn-glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO-B₂O₃-SiO₂-PbO system.

The tested Cu-Sn-Ti alloys exhibit higher resistance to 2-body abrasion compared to the Cu-Sn (90/10) reference material, which has found industrial application as a matrix in saw blade segments used for grinding or cutting ceramics and composites.

The milling time decreases resistance to 2-body abrasion.

The addition of the ceramic phase in the form of glass-crystalline materials from the ZnO-B₂O₃-SiO₂-PbO system in amount of 5% by mass increases the hardness of sintered but are not of a good plastic properties that prevent cracking matrix around the diamond particles, which an indispensable criterion to be fulfilled by the matrix in the sintered metal-diamond tools.

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